

EGYPT AND HELLAS – THE BEGINNING OF KNOWLEDGE EXCHANGE: EUDOXOS OF KNIDOS AS AN EXAMPLE*

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ABSTRACT

In the first half of the fourth century BC Hellenic Astronomy began to move from the stage of contemplative philosophical thought to a new phase of experimentation and practice. Features of this stage became obvious with the contributions of the Hellenic Astronomer Eudoxos, who visited Egypt during the fourth century BC, and probably benefited from its Sciences before the founding of Alexandria. Perhaps the time he spent in Egypt represents one stage of the transmission of Egyptian knowledge to Hellenic Science, which was really developed in Alexandria some decades later. This paper deals with two main debated issues: The first is the exact date Eudoxos visited Egypt; and the second is the kind of knowledge Eudoxos received from learning Egyptian Astronomy and to what extent the late Egyptian Astronomy of his time may have influenced the Hellenic.

I. INTRODUCTION: EUDOXOS' VISIT TO EGYPT

The text which Diogenēs Laertios gives in his *Lives of Philosophers* [*Vitæ Philosophorum*, VIII: 86-91] is our primary source about Eudoxos' life. Diogenēs' text has yet some ambiguity in the names of persons associated with Eudoxos, a matter that makes knowing his exact date of birth and trip to Egypt very complicated.

In his famous *Geōgraphika* [XVII: 1, 29], Strabōn states that in Heliopolis he was shown the school house in which Eudoxos lived during his stay in Egypt, which seems to have been part of a complex of houses for the priests of Heliopolis (perhaps the *House of Life of Heliopolis* ~ *Pr-ḥnh n Twnw*). According to Strabōn, Eudoxos, together with Platōn, spent in Egypt 13 years, while Diogenēs does not associate Eudoxos' visit to Egypt with that of Platōn. Diogenēs speaks about a duration of sixteen months for Eudoxos' stay in Egypt. In Heliopolis, Eudoxos was accompanied by the priest Khnūbis or Khnūphis and kept moving between temples which were the actual places of knowledge. It seems that he involved himself in the habits of the Egyptian priesthood so he shaved his beard and eyebrows as was their tradition¹.

Because the Egyptian priests were known to have been secretive and hesitant to impart their knowledge to the others, to use Strabōn's words: «μυστικούς δὲ καὶ δυσμεταδότους», Eudoxos needed to have a recommendation letter to the Egyptian pharaoh, in order to make his

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¹ Cf. Diogenēs Laertios: *Vitæ Philosophorum*, LCL, 184, xv-xvi: «καὶ τέτταρας μῆνας πρὸς ἐνιαυτῷ διατρίψαντ' αὐτόθι ξυρόμενόν θ' ὑπήνην καὶ ὄφρὺν τὴν Ὀκταετηρίδα κατὰ τινὰς συγγράψαι».

job in Egypt easier. Diogenēs asserts that he had this letter of recommendation from Agēsilaos II, King of Sparta (400-360 BC), to the Pharaoh of Egypt Nektanebō. None of our sources specified to whom of the two Nektanebōs who ruled Egypt at the time, the letter of Agēsilaos was addressed. In order to reveal such an ambiguity, we must refer briefly to some historical events and the relationship between Sparta and Egypt at that time.

During the reign of the Egyptian Pharaoh Nephertēs I (398-393 BC), the first pharaoh of the XXIX Dynasty (398-380 BC), the Persian Empire was a common enemy for both Egypt and Sparta [Xenophōn: *Anabasis*, 1, 4-5]. In year 396 BC, the Persians launched an unsuccessful campaign against Egypt, while during this particular year the Spartan King Agēsilaos stood with the Ionian Islands in their revolt against the Persians. He asked the support of the Egyptian pharaoh who responded positively and immediately sent supplies of wheat and vessels, which the Athenians destroyed at the shores of Rhodos before reaching Sparta [Diodōros Sikelos: XIV, 79]. The following period witnessed the rule of three pharaohs [namely: Psamūthis (393 BC), Akhōris (393-380 BC) and Nephertēs II (380 BC)] who were not interested in alliance with the Spartans and moved to the other party of the Hellenic force represented in Athens and its allies². On the other hand, after the reconciliation of Antalkidas in year 386 BC³, Agēsilaos was fully involved in his struggle with the Thebans (on the one hand) and the revolution of the Messenians who threatened the Spartan borders (on the other). It was of course natural amid the adversity that the Spartan King would not care about the relationship with Egypt.

In 380 BC, the XXX Dynasty took over the rule of Egypt. Nektanebō I, was crowned, in the temple of the goddess Neith in Sais, as the first king of this Dynasty. He ruled Egypt for 18 years⁴. During the first 7 years of his rule, Egypt enjoyed a period of relative peace. However, in 373 BC news of a new attack by Artaxerxēs II reached the pharaoh. This time the Persian king prepared for his expedition a large force of Hellenic mercenaries recruited and commanded by Iphikratēs the Athenian [Diodōros: XV, 41, 1-3]. Nektanebō I, in preparation to face the invasion, soon renewed alliance with the Spartans and recruited a number of mercenaries. Among his preparations was the closing of the seven estuaries of the Nile and the building in front of each of a bulwark protected by a strong garrison, so as to prevent the Persians from entering Egypt via the Nile⁵. The disharmony among the commanders of the invading army on the one hand and the Nile flood on the other were the main factors behind the failure of the campaign and Egypt was temporarily rescued from the Persian occupation [Diodōros: XV, 1-4; 42, 2-5; 43, 1-6]. In the few years to follow, both the Egyptians and the Spartans were involved in their internal problems and the relationship between the two countries became frozen.

In 364 BC the Asian King Maussōlos of Halikarnassos (377/376-353/352 BC) visited Egypt and was the mediator between Egypt and Sparta, where he succeeded in restoring bonds between them [Xenophōn: *Agēsilaos*, II, 1-26]. The renewed friendship between these two countries made Agēsilaos to visit Egypt twice, the first followed his visit to Halikarnassos in 364 BC during the reign of Nektanebō I. This was a short visit as he had to return to Sparta to face

² See CLAYTON, 1994: 172.

³ Generally known as the King's peace between the Persian King Artaxerxēs II (404-358 BC) and the Hellenic Mainland States (XENOPHŌN: *Hellēnika*, V, 1.31), to enforce Persia's hand on the Hellenic Asian States, in order to spare the European States from war.

⁴ See GARDINER, 1987: 406.

⁵ See 'EL-SAYED, 1993: 301-07.

the problems raised by Thēbai. There he began to get prepared for a military combat which was ended up by the battle of Mantinea in 362 BC⁶.

The second visit of Agēsilaos to Egypt was after the battle of Mantinea during the reign of the Pharaoh Tachos or Teōs (362-359 BC), the second king of the XXX Dynasty [Ploutarchos: *Agēsilaos*, XXXVI, 5-6]. Tachos changed the Egyptian policy towards the Persians from defending into offending them. In his preparations for a campaign against the Persians in the region of Syria, he recruited both Athenians and Spartans⁷. King Agēsilaos came to Egypt with an army to assist the pharaoh [Xenophōn: *Agēsilaos*, II, 31]. When the news of a revolution against the pharaoh in his homeland reached the Egyptian-Spartan army stationed in Syria, its leaders have separated and each left in a different way. The deposed pharaoh died before returning home. The junior leader Nektanebō returned to Egypt, where he was declared as Pharaoh by the name Nektanebō II (*Sndm ib R^c, stp n in Hr / Nht Hr hb, Mry Hwt-Hr*: 360-343 BC). The old king of Sparta after contributing to the success of the revolution in favour of the new pharaoh, left to his homeland, but also died on the way [Xenophōn: *Agēsilaos*, II, 31; Ploutarchos, *Agēsilaos*, XXXVII, 3; XL, 2].

Thus the historical conditions reveal the importance of excluding Nektanebō II from any recommendation from Agēsilaos. As was mentioned above, the first seven years of the reign of Nektanebō I witnessed relative peace and a reconstruction movement on a large scale. The Athenian commander Chabrias occupied a prominent place at the pharaoh's court and army, at a time when Agēsilaos was busy enough not to have any external activities until the end of the Messenian revolution in 366 BC. Furthermore, it was not possible for him to be interested in sending any recommendation to the pharaoh who was allied with the Athenians, the traditional enemies of Sparta. After the unsuccessful campaign of the Persians in 373 BC, Egypt has become fully equipped to replace the Athenian allies with loyal Spartans, especially since the most prominent leader of that campaign was the Athenian Iphikratēs. Therefore, the recommendation must have been addressed to Nektanebō I.

If in 364 BC Eudoxos [FIG. I] had taken the decision to go to Egypt; he would have asked King Maussōlos to directly recommend him to the pharaoh during his visit to Egypt that year, as is reported by Xenophōn [*Anabasis*: I, 4-5]. Eudoxos' decision must have come later after his friends helped him in securing the required budget for such a trip, as Diogenēs states. In the occasion of Agēsilaos' visit to Maussōlos, during which Eudoxos was in Halikarnassos, he most probably had asked Maussōlos to help him getting an introductory letter from Agēsilaos who was then a close ally of the Egyptian pharaoh. After becoming fully prepared, our Astronomer set fourth in his intended trip, which must have taken place in 364/363 BC during the reign of Nektanebō I. The year 364 BC agrees with the last year of the 103rd Olympic Games (368-364 BC) which was also a flourishing time for Eudoxos as Diogenēs says⁸. Moreover, this very year, 364 BC, conforms to the time of Leōn of Byzantium⁹, mentioned by Pro-

⁶ The battle of Mantinea took place in 362 BC between the Thebans (led by Epameinōndas) and the Spartans (led by Agēsilaos II) who were actually defeated (on this very battle, see e.g.: the description in the classical work of XENOPHŌN: *Hellēnika*, V, II, 1-3).

⁷ See WHITE, 1970: 203-04.

⁸ This conclusion proves that Strabōn was incorrect when he mentioned that Eudoxos, together with Platōn, had spent thirteen years in Egypt: «συνανέβη γὰρ δὴ τῷ Πλάτωνι ὁ Εὐδόξος δεῦρο, καὶ συνδιέτριψαν τοῖς ἱερῶσιν ἔνταῦθα ἐκείνοι τρισκαίδεκα ἔτη» (*Geōgraphika*: XVII, 29).

⁹ See DE SANTILANA, 1940: 248-62.

klos¹⁰, as being one of Platōn's students and seems to have been a classmate of Eudoxos. Proklos asserts that Eudoxos was younger than Leōn¹¹.

FIGURE I: A medieval imaginary depiction of Eudoxos of Knidos, the famous Mathematician and Astronomer of the Classical Hellenic Antiquity.

Since Diogenēs specified Eudoxos' age during his visit to Egypt by twenty three years, assuming the accuracy of Diogenēs, this means that Eudoxos was born in 387 BC and died at fifty three¹² in 334 BC.

II. EUDOXOS AND THE EGYPTIAN ASTRONOMY

From Diogenēs, we know that Eudoxos studied Astronomy at the hands of Platōn. The possible benefits of Eudoxos from the Egyptian Astronomy were, for a long time, a matter of scientific debate among modern Scholars¹³; although we have documents showing that this was not the case with the ancients who dealt with the works of Eudoxos.

In addition to what was reported by Diogenēs, that during his stay in Egypt, Eudoxos wrote the book called *Oktatēris* (i.e.: *Eight Year Cycle*) and —quoting Eratosthenēs— that Eudoxos' book *Dialogues of Dogs* was a Hellenic translation from an Egyptian one, we find that Eudoxos —according to Diogenēs— before his visit to Egypt, was an active Scholar who used to frequent Schools of Science in order to learn. When returning from Egypt back to his home city of Knidos [FIG. IV], he was received very highly by his citizens and his School attracted many students. His scientific fame became very wide to the extent that he was even entitled

¹⁰ Proklos *apud*: FRASER, 1972: 560, № 56.

¹¹ Cf. «Εὐδοξος δὲ ὁ Κνίδιος, Λέοντος μὲν ὀλίγω νεώτερος, ἑταῖρος δὲ τῶν περὶ Πλάτωνα γενόμενος» (n. 9).

¹² Cf. «διὸ καὶ ὁ ταχέως ἦλθε μόρος, δεκάκις πέντ' ἐπὶ τρισσαῖς εἰσιδόντι Πλειάδας» (Diogenēs Laertios: *Vita Philosophorum*, VIII, 86-91).

¹³ See 'EL-ABBADI, 2000: 53-58.

— as Diogenēs states — *endoxos* which means *the glorious*¹⁴. Could we then maybe assume that Eudoxos' trip to Egypt helped in transforming him to a famous teacher?

Strabōn asserts that in spite of the conservative nature of the Egyptian priests with whom both Platōn and Eudoxos had abided in Heliopolis, these men *excelled in their knowledge of the heavenly bodies*. However, they taught our Hellenic Astronomer *the fractions of the day and night which, running over and above the three hundred and sixty five days, fill out the time of the true year*. Strabōn also confirms that *at that time the true year was unknown among the Hellēnes, as also many other things, until the later astrologers learned from the men who had translated into Hellenic the records of the priests; and even to this day they learn their teachings, and likewise those of the Chaldæans*¹⁵.

Some papyrological testimonies explain how Eudoxos benefited from the Egyptian priests–astronomers. We shall limit our discussion here in two main topics: The Egyptian calendar and the movements of heavenly bodies, as well as the use of the water–clock (*klepshydra*).

III. EUDOXOS AND THE EGYPTIAN CALENDAR

In respect of the first topic, the *Hibeh Papyrus № 27* deals with the calendar¹⁶. This papyrus is dated between 301-298 BC and is one of the earliest Hellenic papyri discovered in Egypt. It represents part of a teaching book written by a Hellenic Astronomer, in which he explains to his students the Egyptian Calendar of Saïs.

The author starts with an introduction, explaining his astronomical theory and his sources [cols. I-III]. He says that he spent five years in the city of Saïs to learn Astronomy at the hands of a *wise man* (*ἀνὴρ σοφός*) [col. II, lines 19-33] who explained to him his theory and practice of Astronomy. However, the author explains that he will summarize what he learned to his disciples [col. II, lines 34-41]. He begins with the years used by the Egyptians [col. I, lines 41-54], and then explains in details the Saïtic Calendar.

Another papyrus which is the famous *Papyrus Paris I* [FIG. III], also known as the *Art of Eudoxos* (*Εὐδόξου Τέχνη*), was written at least a hundred years after the *Hibeh Papyrus*. Its author was a student of Eudoxos¹⁷. Its introduction is very interesting as it begins with a poem in which each verse follows an *ἀκροστιχίς*, starting with a letter of the phrase *Εὐδόξου Τέχνη*.

Studying both documents reveals that there is a big similarity or even a matching in many of their paragraphs. The main topics of both papyri are the Egyptian computations of seasonal changes according to the Spring and Autumn Equinoxes and the Summer and Winter Solstices, their detecting of the Sun's journey from rising to setting and its passing by one constellation to another, the rising and setting of the constellations and stars, how did they fix the

¹⁴ Cf. «Τοῦτον ἀντὶ Εὐδόξου Ἐνδοξον ἐκάλουν διὰ τὴν λαμπρότητα τῆς φήμης». The word *ἔνδοξος* means of high glory/reputation and the word *εὐδοξος* means of good glory/reputation (LIDDELL & SCOTT, 1968: art. «ἔνδοξος» and «εὐδοξος»).

¹⁵ Cf. «οὗτοι δὲ τὰ ἐπιτρέχοντα τῆς ἡμέρας καὶ τῆς νυκτὸς μόρια ταῖς τριακοσίαις ἐξήκοντα πέντε ἡμέρας εἰς τὴν ἐκπλήρωσιν τοῦ ἐνιαυσίου χρόνου παρέδωσαν: ἀλλ' ἠγνοεῖτο τέως ὁ ἐνιαυτὸς παρὰ τοῖς Ἑλλήσιν ὡς καὶ ἄλλα πλείω, ἕως οἱ νεώτεροι ἀστρολόγοι παρέλαβον παρὰ τῶν μεθερμηνευσάντων εἰς τὸ Ἑλληνικὸν τὰ τῶν ἱερέων ὑπομνήματα: καὶ ἔτι νῦν παραλαμβάνουσι τὰ ἀπ' ἐκείνων, ὁμοίως καὶ τὰ τῶν Χαλδαίων» (*Geographika*: XVII, 29).

¹⁶ See GRENFELL & HUNT, 1906: 145-50.

¹⁷ See BLASS, 1997: 3-25.

dates of their religious festivals and kept them unchanged according to the lunar system, and finally the details of the Egyptian Calendar of Saïs.

This similarity between the two documents had pushed Grenfell and Hunt, the publishers of the *Papyrus Hibeh 27*, to define the *wise man* who taught its author as being Eudoxos himself. Yet, this *wise man* was in Saïs, and Eudoxos was never reported by any of our sources to have spent five years in Saïs — if ever had he visited it— a fact that stands in contradiction to this very assumption.

FIGURE II: Part of *Papyrus Paris I: The Art of Eudoxos*.

However, Grenfell and Hunt pointed out to another similarity in the part specifying the dates of religious holidays in their *Papyrus Hibeh 27* with a list of the same holidays written in another Demotic document known as *Papyrus Sallier IV* dated to the Ramesside Period¹⁸. But despite emphasizing similarities between the contents of both papyri, Grenfell and Hunt do not reach the expected result, which is simply that this is an old calendar of Egypt since the time of the Ramesside pharaohs and not a creation of Eudoxos.

El-Abbadi refers to another papyrus preserved in Cairo Museum dated to the Ramesside Period, though this time in hieratic (*Papyrus Cairo 86.637*). It records a calendar of lucky and unlucky days¹⁹. The author of the latter document counts at its end the number of hours of day and night in all the days of the year, where the day was divided into twenty four equal hours that varied in number between day and night. This is consistent with what is mentioned in *Hibeh Papyrus* and partially in *Papyrus Paris I*. The author of *Hibeh* records the hours of the night and day in the period from 20 to 25 Farmouthi (Baramhat), which corresponds to 22 to

¹⁸ See GRENFELL & HUNT, 1906: 145-50.

¹⁹ See EL-ABBADI, 2000: 53-58. [EDITOR'S NOTE: However, the notion of *moment/minute* (*3t*) was never precisely specified or measured before the Hellenistic Period (cf. EG: 206; LÄ, VI, 1986: col. 1372)].

27 June, just as the author of *Cairo Papyrus* did. However, the *hour* (*wnwt*) in *Cairo Papyrus* is the smallest unit of measuring time, while the *Hibeh Papyrus 27* describes how Astronomers in the fourth century BC reached the division of an hour into forty five units or minutes. Thus, it is clear that the Egyptians since the twelfth century BC (Ramesside Period) reached an accurate calendar that calculated the differences in length between night and day. The authors of both the *Hibeh Papyrus* in the fourth century BC and *Papyrus Paris I* [FIG. II] in the early second century BC might have possibly inspired their knowledge from an Egyptian origin that is dated back to the Ramesside Period. *Cairo Papyrus* provides us with some details about how the Egyptians fixed the times of the Equinoxes, how did they also spotted almost correctly the movements of the stars, such are the same topics dealt with in both *Papyrus Hibeh 27* and *Papyrus Paris I*. It can also be concluded that the «wise man» who taught the writer of the *Hibeh Papyrus* was one of the Egyptian priests who had experienced the Saitic Calendar with certainty, just as was the knowledge of Khnūbis, Eudoxos' teacher. It seems that the priests of the temple of Saïs were specialized in one form or another of Astronomy. The proof is that the calendars studied by those Hellenic students, included in the previously mentioned papyri, were always referred to as Saitic Calendars.

Hekataios of Abdēra, the historian of the fourth century BC who came to Egypt with the arrival of Alexander the Great, claims, as quoted by Diodōros [I: 81, 4-5], that the Egyptians used to keep an accurate record of the movements of each star over many years, and had managed through astronomical records and observations to predict earthquakes and floods, as well as the appearance of comets.

The Egyptian knowledge of the celestial bodies and the movements of the stars go back to the Pre-Dynastic Period as it can be inferred from some funerary drawings that show different shapes of asterisms and their names²⁰. From the time of Dynasty III (2686-2613 BC), they began to create the earliest stellar calendar ever in history, using special bright stars of certain constellations called *Decans* (*b3w ʿnhw / ntrw imyw pt / knmtyw*). They selected a number of the regularly rising stars that are most conspicuous and divided them into 36 groups corresponding to the 36 parts of the year, each composed of 10 days, hence the name *Decans*, each part beginning with the rising of one group of stars and ending with its setting²¹. The first star group is marked by the heliacal rising of the *shining star* Sōthis or Sirius (α -CMA, Egyptian: *Spdt*)²², which corresponds to the flooding of the Nile. They completed the year into 365 days by adding 5 epagomenal days of festivals and celebration of their principal deities²³. The recently discovered parts of what is known as the *Naos of the Decades* testifies that the Decanal Calendar remained invariable until the end of the Dynastic Period. It is a monolithic small shrine of black granite erected by Nektanebō I, the first pharaoh of the XXX Dynasty. Its outer facades are decorated with 36 vertical fields devoted to the 36 decades of the year and a 37th field is inserted for the 5 leap days which complete the 365 days of the decanal year²⁴ [on this very artefact and the decans, see also the extended articles by F. GODDIO and by A.-S. VON BOMHARD in the present volume: pp. 181-87 & 163-79, respectively].

²⁰ See SLOLEY, 1942: 161.

²¹ See LOCHER, 1992: 201-07; MARAVELIA, 2006: 446-52.

²² See MARAVELIA, 2006: 25, 299, 300 & fig. III.11, 449 & Tab. 4: № 2.

²³ See VON BOMHARD, 2000: 137-45; MARAVELIA, 2006: 460 & Tab. 11.

²⁴ The upper part of this shrine was found in 1777 at Kanōpos and was kept in the Louvre. In 1934 Prince 'Omar Toussoun salvaged the shrine's back wall and the plinth from the Bay of Kanōpos and dedicated it to the Helleno-Roman Museum of Alexandria (YOYOTTE, 1954: 79-82). In 2000 the left lateral *façade* and part of the right were salvaged during the underwater excavations carried out in the Bay of Kanōpos by the IEASM Mission directed by Frank Goddio (see VON BOMHARD, 2006: 49-52).

During the time of the XXX Dynasty, the harbour of Kanōpos was the only Egyptian maritime entrance to receive comers from the Mediterranean Sea, as Hērodotos states [II: 178-179]. Therefore, would it be here possible to go with our imagination, assuming that Eudoxos when entering Egypt might have looked into the calendar inscribed at the *Naos of the Decades*? In Heliopolis he was probably taught the Egyptian calendar of the decades which was in use in his time²⁵ and celebrated by the pharaoh who introduced him to *the sacred scribes* (ἱερογραμματεῖς), so as to use the words of both the authors of *Papyrus Hibeh 27* and *Papyrus Paris I*.

IV. EUDOXOS AND THE WATER-CLOCK (KLEPSHYDRA) – CONCLUSIONS

In his *De Architectura*, Vitruvius tells us that Eudoxos used the water-clock in his calculations of time²⁶. According to the archaeological evidence the Egyptians had used the water-clock (named by the Hellenes ὠρολογιον/*hōrologhion*²⁷ or κλεψύδρα), in order to calculate as precisely as possible the hours of the night.

The water-clock depended in its early examples on the distillation of water from a small hole in the bottom of a stone pot that had nearly a conical shape. The bowl was divided from the inside, sometimes from the outside, to twelve vertical sections that represented the months of the year. Each month-section was divided, in its turn, into twelve degrees, each representing one of the twelve *hours of night* (*wnt nt grh*). These sections and grades were used to determine the level of the reduction of water every hour, taking into account the different duration of the hours, according to the seasons and the months. It seems that later on, the development of the water-clock was to turn from the water-filled pot into an empty cylindrical bowl in which the water dropped from another pot, in order to determine the degree of fullness of the vessel.

From the first type, the oldest known Egyptian *klepsychra* ever discovered, it was made of alabaster [FIG. III] and dates back to the reign of Amūnhotep III (1391-1353 BC). It was manufactured by a scientist named Amūnemhat whose achievements were recorded on the walls of his tomb²⁸.

In the British Museum there is a water-clock [BM EA 933] made of black granite discovered in the Delta. Its external walls are inscribed with illustrative writings. On the main frieze are two representations of Alexander the Great, one shows Alexander offering the water vessel to the god Khonsū, Egyptian god of the Moon, who wears a Moon-like crown and holds a sceptre. The god in turn provides the *ḥnḥ*-sign (𐎃) to Alexander who is depicted as a pharaoh. The second scene depicts Alexander offering incense to a god whose features are blurred. The uppermost frieze of the vessel contains some prayers to the king (Alexander), while the bottom combines hieroglyphs and signs showing the movement of the zodiac and the stars

²⁵ The relief of the Zodiac in the ceiling of the pronaos at the temple of Dendara (dated to 50 BC) represents the first map of the sky according to the Egyptian calendar. It also gives an idea about the *dōdekatēmoría* or the twelve signs of the zodiac created during the Ptolemaic Period (ROGERS, 1998: 9-28; MARAVELIA, 2006: 17 & nn 19-20, 269 & fig. III.9, 444 & fig. 1).

²⁶ Cf. «Item sunt ex aqua conquisitæ ab eisdem scriptoribus horologiorum rationes, [...]» (VITRUVIUS: *De Architectura*, VIII, 1, 2).

²⁷ EDITOR'S NOTE: We must not, of course, confuse this ὠρολόγιον with the homonymous astronomical instrument of the Egyptians (*mrḥt*), used to observe the stars (see e.g.: BORCHARDT, 1899: 10-17; MARAVELIA, 2006: 250). See, however, LÄ, VI, 1986, cols 1156-57: art. «Wasseruhr».

²⁸ See MURRAY, 1949: 249-50. For the tomb decoration of Amūnemhat, cf. POGO, 1939: 403-25.

in the sky. The inner part of the pot is divided into twelve columns with grading lines that differ in shape from one column to another to distinguish between the twelve months of the year. It appears from the hole on the circular base of the pot that the clock was of the type depending on emptying the water. Once again papyrial sources provide evidence of the knowledge of the Hellēnes and especially Eudoxos as to what the Egyptians succeeded in the astronomical calculation of time using the water-clock. The author of the *Hibeh Papyrus 27* states that his *wise man* taught him *the complete truth which he practically proved using a stone instrument which the Hellēnes called Gnōmōn*²⁹.

FIGURE III: The famous Karnak *klepsydra*, rich in astronomical depictions (of decans, northern constellations, month-deities and planets), dated from the era of Amūnhotep III [Archæological Museum of Cairo, JE 37.525].

Another source dated to the third century AD, namely *Papyrus Oxyrrhynchus 470*, is mainly concerned with this³⁰. This papyrus is part of a scientific book specialized in describing astronomical instruments. Its second part (lines 31 to the end of the papyrus) deals with *klepsydrai* of the type which depends on the emptying of water from the cylindrical graded vessel. The papyrus describes exactly how to make this cylindrical vessel and how to inscribe its inner walls with vertical graded lines using the Egyptian unit of measurement, the *finger*/δάκτυλος (*db*⁵). The text includes names of Egyptian origin transliterated into Hellenic. It specifies the measurements of the vessel: the upper radius is 24 fingers, the lower 12, the height 18. These standards were consistent with the water-clock invented by Amūnemhat in the sixteenth century BC.

Now it becomes clear that the young man of the fourth century BC, the author of the *Hibeh Papyrus 27*, and the young man of the early second century BC, who wrote *Papyrus Paris I*, as well as the young man of the third century AD, the author of *Papyrus Oxyrrhynchus 470*, had gained (at least some of) their knowledge from an Egyptian origin which was more than 1,000 years earlier. And possibly part of what Eudoxos himself learned on the calendar and

²⁹ See lines 20-28 «πᾶσαν οὖν τὴν ἀλήθει-/ [αν] ἡμῖν ἐξετίθει καὶ ἐπ[ι] | [το]ῦ ἔργου ἐδείκνυον ἐ- | [κ το]ῦ ὀλμου τοῦ λιθίνου | [ὁς ἐκ]αλεῖτο Ἑλληνιστὶ | [γν]ώμων». See also n. 15, *supra*.

³⁰ See GRENFELL & HUNT 1899-1916: 141-46.

the measuring of time was of Egyptian origin³¹. Eudoxos studied the Astronomy of Pythagoras and the astronomical rules of Platōn. The period he spent in Egypt possibly had a significant impact on the enrichment of his astronomical thinking, especially after receiving lessons in Astronomy by the Egyptian priests, so maybe he collected some of the fruits of several schools that were not available to others who preceded him.

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³¹ EDITOR'S NOTE: See, however, DREYER, ²1953: 88, n. 3; Chapter IV: *passim*; but mainly see the opposite and well-founded opinion of Sauneron in SAUNERON, ³2000: 114-15.